

Optimum Sizing and Siting for DG Units using Hybrid 2/3 Rule and Harmony Search Algorithm

Abdulsalam A. Aloukili, Metwally A. El-Sharkawy, Mahmoud A. Attia

Abstract—The electrical energy one of most important basics of modern life and the demand on this energy increase consciously. Which make some challenges to operators to increase the generation to feed the growing demand. This growth lead to extend the centralized plant to provide distribution network by required energy also lead them to develop transmission system. This method is so costly where it is required money to extend the power system. An appearance of distributed generation DG is considered a solution for these problems and can reduce the cost where it provides the load by electricity in customer side without passing through transmission system. While the aim target from DG is supporting the grid and improve power quality, voltage profile, reduction of power losses and reliability. In this paper will discuss sizing and siting the distributed generation in the grid. In this work introduced hybrid method where it is used 2/3 rule and harmony search algorithm to find optimum location and sizing respectively. This work is done under several loading cases up to 250 % from normal load also compared with other researches in this filed used the same model (IEEE 33 bus radial distribution system) that used in this paper. MTLAB software used to complete this research.

Keywords— harmony search algorithm, distributed generation and 2/3 rule.

I. INTRODUCTION

Last decades DG becomes more important due to meet the growth demand without needing to upgrade the transmission system (overhead, cables and transformers). Also the centralized power station should be extended to produce enough power meet the demand of load. Recently, using DG as power source in customer side is to feed those increasing demand. Where many researches studied the impact of DG units on distributed system where has positive and negative

impact on system performance as voltage profile, losses (active and reactive power) and protective devices. [1,2]

The impact of DG on the system performance is depending on position and size of DG units. Where Authors of [3] speak about that the installation of small DG-PV units near the customer is very attractive to utilities and consumers due to the energy produced close the loads. The distributed generation (DG) always installed at sub transmission network. Where the main aims are to:

- ✓ Reduce transmission lines losses
- ✓ Improve voltage profile on system
- ✓ Reduce the emission from centralized plant
- ✓ Low operating cost due to peak shaving
- ✓ Reduced or deferred investment in generation, transmission, transformers and distribution infrastructure upgrades due to relieve T&D congestion

To get best performance to distributed generation on power system many researchers proposed several studied include a lot of methods to get the optimum place and size of DG to improve the voltage profile and power losses. Some researches assumed the location of DG depend on availability of renewable source (sun, wind seas and Ocean or etc.) in media and it's space [3], also other researchers in by H.L. willis [4]. used simple analytical approach techniques as 2/3 rule which is based on installing the DG on 2/3 of feeder by sizing of DG's estimated as 2/3 the value of loads but this techniques not use in uniformly distributive load due to this techniques follow the method of exact loss formula where the size of DG determine by calculate direct equation prevail from the generalized reduced gradient (GRG) method..

In [5], PSO algorithm is used to find the optimum size of DG and the location of DG is limited by Loss Sensitivity Factor LSF and WK bus. Also Zhu and others in [6] are suggested method called Ordinal Optimization to find optimal location and size of DG with keep the balance between loss minimization and capacity maximization. A. Keane et al [7] used linear programming to DG problem.

In [8], A. M. El. Zonkely proposed Sequential quadratic programming (SQP) to find placement of DG without consideration fault restraints suggested. Also in [9] the authors

Abdulsalam A. Aloukili: Electrical Power and Machines Department, Faculty of Engineering, Ain Shams University, Cairo, Egypt, Email: a_alaokali@yahoo.com.

Metwally A. El-Sharkawy: Electrical Power and Machines Department, Faculty of Engineering, Ain Shams University, Cairo, Egypt, Email: metwallyalsharkawy@yahoo.com.

Mahmoud A. Attia: Electrical Power and Machines Department, Faculty of Engineering, Ain Shams University, Cairo, Egypt, Email: Mahmoud.Abdullah@eng.asu.edu.eg.

used multi objective function to reduce losses by insertion DG units in optimum allocated. In [10], M. Shaaban and Petinrin proposed method to minimize losses and improve power voltage profile via using combination of sensitivity index, exact loss formula and voltage sensitivity coefficient.

Genetic Algorithm one of oldest search method where based on natural is chosen to get optimum sizing and siting of DG units to minimize losses [11,12]. L. Wang et al. in [13] used Ant Colony optimization to get the optimum location and size of DG units where this search method based on ant behavior to find shortest way from den to food please also search for food.

R.S. Rao et al. [14] used Harmony search to find the optimum site of DG which was depend on the loss sensitivity factor to reduce losses and improve voltage profile in a system. In [15], N.G.A. Hemdan et al. used Particle Heuristic Algorithm to find optimum place of DG where based on the resumption of flow power presented. This technique contains two methods which are clustering techniques and exhaustive search.

Impact of distributed generation in voltage regulation

One of the troubles occurs to far-end of radial distribution system or in the rural is dip on voltage. This made some problem to loads and protective device. The voltage profile can be supported and improved by using tap change transformer, shunt capacitor switched on feeder and shifting transformer towards the load center. According for several researches the previous techniques can keep the voltage in the required limit. According to [16] the place and size of DG has important effect in voltage profile. Also when using improved analytical (IA-method) the minimum voltage increase to more acceptable limit. According to American National Standards in voltage fluctuation on distribution systems is within range (+7% to -13%) but in practical many companies keep voltage fluctuation within $\pm 6\%$ which should be considered in any solution suggested to enhance voltage profile. One of the methods used to control on voltage profile in customer side as in [17]. The concept is insertion DG in distribution system as capacitor bank with the DG units inject real power or both active and reactive power where most distributed generation work at between ranges 0.85 lagging to unity power factor. Also the inverter connected to photovoltaic, wind turbine or any DC source to provide the system via leading power factor. All previous cases lead to improve voltage profile when select optimum places and size especially in rural and far-end of distribution system. Also reduce all substation capacities from distribution system. Other researches talk about the bad position of DG can be lead to worst system performance [18,19].

Impact of distributed generation in power losses

One of the important solution can DG introduce in distribution network is to reduce power losses in distribution system. Where several researches appear ability of reduce both

active and reactive power losses by inject DG units also increase reliability of system [20].

As appear in [21], the both active and reactive losses in distribution system can be reducing by inserting DG in optimum location and sizing. Several researches apply this concept by injecting both active and reactive power in distribution system which reduce losses and improve ability of system [16,19]. But the most important rule to insert DG units to improve system performance is selection optimum location and sizing to the DG units in distribution system. Authors of [21] considered concept of DG units exactly as capacitor bank but a capacitor bank produce the grid just by reactive power. In [16] Authors used two different methods to select the placement and size of DG units. The active power losses in the system without DG was around 202.677 kW and after use Improved analytical IM-method to find site and size of DG units the losses reduction to 110.1537 kW and by use PSO the losses reduce decrease to 92.4365 kW [16].

In this paper hybrid method is proposed by using both 2/3 rule and harmony search algorithm to find optimum placement and sizing of DG units. 2/3 rule is used to find the location of DGs and harmony search is used to find the optimal sizing of DGs at several loading conditions.

II. METHODOLOGY

This part of paper will introduce the mechanism to select the location of DGs and DGs sizing. This operation is important to minimize the losses and improve voltage profile to the selection system. In this research the sizing for DG is studied in many cases 100%, 150% 200% and 250% from normal load and the siting will be fixed for all cases. IEEE 33 bus radial distribution system was selected.. The total load of system is (3581KW& 1745KVAR). Fig.1 shows IEEE 33 bus.

Figure 1. IEEE 33 bus radial distribution system

Backward/Forward Sweep Method of power flow is used in this paper to obtain the voltage at each bus and the active & reactive power losses in each branch of the system [24]. Table.1 shows the voltage at each bus and power losses at each branch by using Backward/ Forward Sweep Method.

TABLE I. IEEE 33 BUS DATA WITHOUT DG UNIT

Branch	Power Loss (KW)	Reactive loss (KVar)	Bus	Voltage (p.u)
1	13.6400	6.9531	1	1.0000
2	56.4646	28.7592	2	0.9964
3	20.6039	10.4934	3	0.9794
4	19.1936	9.7756	4	0.9705
5	39.0578	33.7165	5	0.9618
6	2.1213	7.0121	6	0.9411
7	5.3191	1.7578	7	0.9374
8	4.5562	3.2734	8	0.9315
9	3.8563	2.7334	9	0.9242
10	0.5958	0.1970	10	0.9175
11	0.9502	0.3142	11	0.9164
12	2.8786	2.2648	12	0.9146
13	0.7903	1.0403	13	0.9076
14	0.3964	0.3528	14	0.9051
15	0.3083	0.2252	15	0.9035
16	0.2738	0.3656	16	0.9019
17	0.0571	0.0448	17	0.8997
18	0.2088	0.1992	18	0.8991
19	1.0760	0.9696	19	0.9957
20	0.1302	0.1521	20	0.9910
21	0.0563	0.0745	21	0.9901
22	3.8420	2.6252	22	0.9893
23	6.1978	4.8941	23	0.9749
24	1.5431	1.2074	24	0.9665
25	2.3500	1.1970	25	0.9623
26	2.9464	1.5002	26	0.9388
27	9.7751	8.6185	27	0.9359
28	6.5969	5.7471	28	0.9237
29	3.1339	1.5963	29	0.9149
30	1.8333	1.8119	30	0.9109
31	0.2430	0.2833	31	0.9062
32	0.0140	0.0217	32	0.9052
33	zero	zero	33	0.9049
Total Losses	211.0103	140.1770	Min VOLT	0.8991

A. Location of DG

The location of DG is not less important than sizing of DG where the wrong location for distributed generation lead to increase losses to the system and not support the grid also sometimes caused increasing in the voltage more that demand which produced over voltage. In this paper 2/3 rule is used to find location of DG where this method widely used in several application of power system especially in FACTS where this method so easy to apply in any feeder which based on install DG at 2/3 of feeder by 2/3 of capacity of load but in this research using this method just to location of DG. And by looking to Fig.1 the IEEE 33 BUS and by referring to 2/3 rule the buses selected as location to the distributed generation are (13, 21, 24 and 31) where those sites will be fixed to all cases

of loading (100%, 150% 200% and 250% from normal load) and the change will be just in sizing of distributed generation.

B. Sizing of DG

To find optimum size for distributed generation Harmony search algorithm is used in this work. This technique run the power flow program several times and at each process the harmony memory used new data and save the best solution. In this research processed the sizing operation four times at each case use new sizing to the new develop in the grid (100%, 150% 200% and 250% from normal load). The distributed generation produces only active power (unity power factor).

Harmony Search algorithm (HS): Recently proposed a new heuristic optimization technique inspired from music phenomenon. The procedures of solution. by HS algorithm are to. Initialize the design parameters at first, then harmony memory (HM) is initialized. After that a New Harmony improvisation is created from the HM, then. Harmony memory is. Updated. Finally, the procedure is repeated starting from harmony memory improvisation until the criteria. of termination is satisfied [25, 26]. The flowchart of the HS algorithm is shown in Fig. 2

Figure 2. Flow Chart of Harmony Search algorithm

III. RESULT

In first case at 100% loading the DG installed at (13, 21, 24 and 31) where the harmony search select rating for each bus around (595, 200, 285 and 599) KW present around % 45 from load. The voltage in system is reached to 0.9526 pu from 0.8991 and the losses are reduced to 72.27KW which present 2.01% from load and the reactive losses are reduced to 47.71KVAR that present around 2.73%. Where the losses

before insert the DG were 211KW (5.89%) and 140.17KVAR present 8.03%. Also can see clear different on voltage at each bus as shown in Fig.3.

TABLE II. SYSTEM AT 100% LOADING

Case of system	Minimum voltage pu	Maximum voltage pu	Active power losses		Reactive power losses	
			kW	%	KVAr	%
Without DG	0.8991	1	211.013	5.89%	140.1770	8.03%
With DG (1680 kW) 45% of loading	0.9526	1	72.273	2.01%	47.7134	2.73%

Figure 3. voltages at each bus case 100% from normal load

In second case at 150% loading where the system load is (5371KW & 2617.5KVAR) where the value of DG selected by HS are (1000, 500 500 and 1000) KW present around 55 % of loading. And by looking to Table 3 it can be seen that the minimum voltage is increased to 0.9378 pu and the losses in system are reduced to 2.8% & 3.8% of loading for both active and reactive losses. And by increasing the DG rating to (4579KW) 85% the losses are reduced to 2.06 % & 2.9% of loading for active and reactive power and the voltage is reached to 0.9637pu. System result described in Table.3 .Fig.4 show the voltage at each bus at 150% loading.

TABLE III. SYSTEM AT 150% LOADING

Case of system	Minimum voltage pu	Maximum voltage pu	Active power losses		Reactive power losses	
			Active power losses (KW)	Active power losses (%)	Reactive power losses (KVA)	Reactive power losses (%)
Without DG	0.8412	1	522.9711 KW	9.73%	348.0025 KVA	13.2%
With DG (3000 kW) 55% of loading	0.9378	1	150.4276 KW	2.8%	100.0809 KVA	3.8%
With DG (4579 kW) 85% of loading	0.9637	1	110.7010 KW	2.06%	77.6112 KVA	2.9%

Figure 4. voltage at each bus case 150% from normal load

In third case when using 200% loading (7162KW & 3490 kVA) the harmony search selected the rating for DG as (802,609,772 and 1900) KW around 56% from load. The DGs are at buses (13, 21 24 and 31) which caused increasing in voltage to reach 0.8918 pu and the losses reduction to 3.91% & 5.54% of loading for both active and reactive power losses from 14.58% & 19.95%. When increasing the DG rating to (6170 KW) which present 86% the losses are reduced to 2.7% & 3.99% of loading for both active and reactive power losses

and the minimum voltage reach to 0.9546 pu as appear in Tabel.4 . Fig 5 displayed the voltage at each bus.

TABLE IV. SYSTEM AT 200% LOADING

Case of system	Minimum voltage pu	Maximum voltage pu	Active power losses		Reactive power losses	
			Active power losses (KW)	Active power losses (%)	Reactive power losses (KVA)	Reactive power losses (%)
Without DG	0.7766	1	1.0446e+3 KW	14.58%	696.5683 KVA	19.95%
With DG (4075 kW) 56% of loading	0.8918	1	280.6055 KW	3.91%	193.4003 KVA	5.54%
With DG (6170 kW) 86% of loading	0.9546	1	198.3354 KW	2.7%	139.4459 KVA	3.99%

Figure 5. voltages at each bus case 200% from normal load

In last case when using 250% loading (8952KW & 4362KVAR) the harmony search select rating for DGs as (1500,709,892 and 2201) KW present around 59% from load. The DGs are installed at buses (13, 21 24 and 31) which caused increasing in voltage to reach 0.8953 pu and the losses are reduced to 4.50% & 6.29% of loading for both active and reactive power losses from 21.10% & 28.9%. last case when increasing the rating of DG units to (7816 KW) which present 87% of the load, the minimum voltage in the system is reached to 0.9505 pu and the losses are reduced to 3.47% and 5.03% of

loading for active and reactive losses. As displayed in Tabel.5. Fig 6 display the voltage at each bus.

TABLE V. SYSTEM AT 250% LOADING

Case of system	Minimum voltage pu	Maximum voltage pu	Active power losses		Reactive power losses	
Without DG	0.7039	1	1.8893e+3 kW	21.10%	1.2632e+3 kVAr	28.9%
With DG (5302 kW) 59% of loading	0.8953	1	403.3315 kW	4.50%	274.7843 kVAr	6.29%
With DG (7816 kW) 87% of loading	0.9505	1	311.7798 kW	3.47%	219.4653 kVAr	5.03%

Figure 6. voltages at each bus case 250% from normal load

By looking for Table 7 where Displays the priority in voltage and the losses in system where can see clear advantage on minimum voltage and the total losses in the system in the method used in this paper than others two methods (Improved analytical IA & PSO) that used in [16] to find optimum sizing and siting. Fig 6 shows the voltage at each bus in those cases.

TABLE VI. COMPARISON BETWEEN IMPROVED ANALYTICAL IA METHOD, PSO METHOD AND(2/3 RULE & HARMONY)

Method	DG Rating kW	Min voltage pu	Max voltage pu	Active Power losses kW	Reactive power losses kVAr
AI method[16]	2560.2300	0.957416	1	110.1537	non
PSO method[16]	1857.5	0.940027	1	92.4365	non
2/3& harmony	1685	0.9526	1	72.2734	47.7134

Figure 7. voltage at each Bus 100% loading

CONCLUSION

In this paper introduced 2/3 rule with harmony method to select the optimum location and sizing for DG units at many several loading conditions. Where in each case the insertion of DGs into the system can reduce the losses in system and improve the voltage profile. Also in case with DGs have high rating; the losses and the voltage profile are better. By looking to the last comparison between the 2/3 rule with harmony showed the priority of this optimization techniques on Improved analytical IA method and PSO where used less rating of DG, improve the voltage profile and reduce the losses better than other cases.

REFERENCES

[1] Aquino-Lugo A. A., Klump R., Overbye T. J. A control framework for the smart grid for voltage support using agent-based technologies. *IEEE Transactions on Smart Grid*. 2011;2(1):161-168. doi: 10.1109/TSG.2010.2096238

[2] Philip P. Barker and Robert W. de Mello, "Determining the Impact of Distributed Generation on Power Systems: Part -1 radial DG systems", *Power Engineering Society Summer Meeting*, 2000.

[3] P. Chiradeja and R. Ramakumar, "An Approach to Quantify the Technical Benefits of Distributed Generation," *IEEE Trans. on Energy Conversion*, Vol. 19, No. 4, pp. 1686- 1693, December 2004.

[4] H. L. Willis, "Analytical methods and rules of thumb for modelling DG-distribution interaction", *IEEE*, 2000.

[5] Ambika. R and Rajeswari .R." Optimal Siting and Sizing of Multiple DG Units for the Enhancement of Voltage Profile and Loss Minimization in Transmission Systems Using Nature Inspired Algorithms "*ScientificWorldJournal*. 2016; 2016: 1086579. Published online 2016 Feb 8. doi: 10.1155/2016/1086579 <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC4761755/>

[6] Zhu, R.P. Broadwater, Tam, K.-S., Seguin, R., As-geirsson, H. "Impact of DG Placement on Reliability and Efficiency with Time-Varying

Loads" *IEEE Trans. Power Syst.*, Vol. 21, No. 1, pp. 419-427, Feb .. (2006),

[7] A.Keane and O'Malley, "Optimal Allocation of Embedded Generation on Distribution Networks", *IEEE Trans. Power Syst.*, Vol. 20, No. 3, pp. 1640-1646, Aug. M. (2005),

[8] A.M.EI-Zonkoly, "Optimal Placement of Multi-distributed Generation Units Including Different Load models using Particle Swarm Optimization", *IETGener., Transm., Distrib.*, Vol. 5, No. 7, pp. 760-771, Jul. (2011)

[9] Le, A.D.T., Kashem, M.A., Negnevitsky, M. and Ledwich, G. "Optimal Distribution Generation Parameters for Reducing Losses with Economic Consideration" *Power Engineering Society Gener. Meeting IEEE*, pp.I-8. (2007),

[10] M. Shaaban, and Petinrin, "Sizing and Siting of DG in Distribution System for Voltage Profile Improvement and Loss Reduction," *IJSGCE Gener.*, Vol. 8, No. 1, pp. 1-7. (2013),

[11] Mohamad Amiri, Mina SheikholeslamiKandelousi, and Mahmood Moghadasian" *Distribution Feeder Reconfiguration Considering Distributed Generators using Cuckoo Optimization Algorithm "* 2nd International Conference on Research in Science, Engineering and Technology (ICRSET'2014), March 21-22, 2014 Dubai (UAE)

[12] Kim, IO., Nam, S.W., Park, S.K. and Singh, C. "Dispersed Generation Planning using Improved Hereford Ranch Algorithm", *Elect. Power Syst. Res.*, Vol. 47, No. 1, pp. 47-55, Oct(1998).

[13] L.Wang, and C. Singh,"Reliability-constrained Optimum Placement of Reclosers and Distributed Generators in Distribution Networks using an ant Colony System Algorithm", *IEEE Trans. Syst., Man, Cybern. C, Appl. Rev.*, Vol. 38, No.6, pp. 757-764, Nov. (2008)

[14] R.S.Rao, , K.Ravindra, , K.Satish, and S. Narasimham, V.L., "Power Loss minimization in Distribution System using Network Reconfiguration in the Presence of Distributed Generation", *IEEE TRANSACTIONS ON POWER SYSTEMS*, VOL. 28, NO. 1, FEBRUARY 2013

[15] N.G.A. Hemdan, and Kurat, M., "Efficient Integration of Distributed Generation for Meeting the Increased Load Demand", *In!. J. Electr. Power EnergySyst.*, Vol. 33, No. 9, pp. 1572-1583, Nov. 2011.

[16] T. Ravi Kumar and G. Kesava Rao " Analysis of IA and PSO Algorithms for Siting and sizing of DG in Primary Distribution Networks " *International Journal of Control Theory and Applications*

[17] J. Kilonzi Charles, N. AbunguOdero" Effects of Distributed Generation penetration on system power losses and voltage profiles" *International*

Journal of Scientific and Research Publications , ISSN 2250-3153, Volume 3, Issue 12, December 2013

- [18] W. EL-KHATTAM & M. M. A. SALAMA " Impact of Distributed Generation on Voltage Profile in Deregulated Distribution System "
- [19] Sani A. Muhammad1, Bello Muhammad2 and Hamza Abdullahi3" THE EFFECT OF DISTRIBUTED GENERATION ON POWER SYSTEM PROTECTION A-REVIEW " International Journal of Electrical and Electronics Engineers , ISSN- 2321-2055 (E) , IJEEE, Vol. No.7, Issue No. 01, Jan-June, 2015
- [20] Philip P. Barker, R. W. "Determining the Impact of Distributed Generation on Power Systems" Part 1 - Radial Distribution Systems. 12. IEEE. Retrieved 02 16, 2011, from IEEE. (2000).
- [21] Angel FernándezSarabia" Impact of distributed generation on distribution system "thesis introduce to Master in Dissertation Submitted to the Faculty of Engineering, Science and Medicine, Aalborg University in Partial Fulfilmen. Aalborg, Denmark. june ,2011

- [22] Philip P. Barker and Robert W. de Mello, "Determinin g the Impact of Distributed Generation on Power Systems: Part -1 radial DG systems", Power Engineering Society Summer Meeting, 2000
- [23] Mohamed Talal Mohamed Elmathana" The Effect of Distributed Generation on Power System Protection" thesis for the degree of Masters by Research, Presented to the University of Exeter, September 2010
- [24] G. W. Chang ; S. Y. Chu ; H. L. Wang "An Improved Backward/Forward Sweep Load Flow Algorithm for Radial Distribution Systems", IEEE Transactions on Power Systems Volume: 22, Issue: 2, May 2007.
- [25] Ibrahim M. Diao, Niveen M. Badra and Mahmoud A. Attia, "Harmony Search Algorithm and Teaching-Learning-Based Optimization Approaches to Enhance Power System Performance"issue 10, vol. 34 , World Applied Sciences Journal (WASJ), 2016.
- [26] Z. Geem, J. Kim, et aI. , "A new heuristic optimization algorithm: harmony search," Simulation 76 (2) (2001) 60-68 .

Abdulsalam Aref Aloukli got his B.Sc Degree in Electrical Power and Machines from omer el-mokhtar University, dernah/ libya and studing in Master of Science - Electrical Engineering Electrical Power & Machines in Ain Shams University, Cairo, Egypt. also he works at

IRASA network as Project Engineer

M. A. El-Sharkawy was born in Daqahliyya, Egypt in 1942. He received the B. Sc. Degree (Honors) and M. Sc. Degree in Electrical Engineering from Ain-Shams University in Cairo, Egypt in 1964 and 1970, respectively. He received the Ph. D. degree from the Polytechnic Institute of Leningrad in the former Soviet Union

in 1974. Currently he is emeritus professor of Electric Power Engineering in Ain Shams University. Dr. Sharkawy had been Professor of Electric Power Engineering in Ain Shams University since 1987. Dr. Sharkawy has supervised a large number of Ph. D. and M. Sc. research works in Electric Power Engineering. He is the author and co-author of many published refereed papers. Dr. Sharkawy is also a Professional Engineer since 1987. He designed and supervised the construction of electrical and electro-mechanical systems of a large number of big projects in Egypt and Saudi Arabia.

Mahmoud Abdallah Attia, He received B.Sc., M.Sc. and Ph.D. in electrical engineering from Ain Shams University (ASU), Egypt in 2005, 2010 and 2015 respectively. He has joined ASU teaching staff since 2007. He authored many journal and conference papers. He is a reviewer for power component and systems journal, Ain

Shams Engineering Journal Elsevier and International Transactions on Electrical Energy Systems. 2009, He was in Technical committee of ASU international conference ASCEE-3. He is a Member of "Continuous Improvement & Quality Assurance Unit of Faculty of engineering ASU". He is the author of books 'Optimal Allocation of FACTS Devices in Electrical Power Systems: A Genetic Algorithm Based Approach', in April 2013 and 'Enhancing Power System Performance with Growing Wind Power Penetration: optimal Allocation of FACTS', in July 2015 LAP LAMBERT Academic Publishing.